

Amino Derivatives of Tungsten (VI) Oxytetrachloride. Part I

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The amino derivatives of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride have been prepared by the action of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride on some mono- and diamines, their properties studied and structures discussed.

Very little work appears to have been done on the formation of the compounds of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride with amines and heterocyclic bases in organic solvents. Rideal (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1889, 55, 41) obtained W_2N_3 by the action of dry ammonia on $WOCl_4$ in the cold. Rosenheim and Jacobssohn (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1906, 50, 297) obtained $WO_3 \cdot 3NH_3$ by heating WO_3Cl_2 with liquid ammonia under pressure. The authors have already studied the formation of compounds of WCl_6 with organic bases (this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 588; 1961, 28, 182; 1961, 38, 177). The work has now been extended to study the formation of compounds by treating tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride with primary mono- and diamines in organic solvents.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines used were of Merck or B. D. H. 'extra pure' quality. The organic solvents were dried and distilled. Tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride was prepared by heating a mixture of tungsten trioxide and sugar charcoal first in a current of dry CO_2 until all the air and moisture were expelled, and then in a current of dry chlorine. Excess of chlorine was removed by passing dry CO_2 . It was then distilled in a current of CO_2 and extracted with carbon disulphide.

General Method of Preparation—A solution of the amine in benzene was slowly added to $WOCl_4$ solution with constant shaking till the precipitation was complete and the amine was in slight excess. In the case of toluidines, only a slight precipitate appeared on the addition of the amine solution and much of the compound separated after allowing the mixture to stand overnight in a desiccator over $CaCl_2$. It was filtered and washed with benzene till free of the amine. All these operations were carried out in a dry atmosphere. The precipitate was filter-pressed and finally dried in a vacuum desiccator.

Chlorine was estimated by Piria and Schiff's method, tungsten as WO_3 , and nitrogen in few cases by Kjeldahl's method.

General Properties.—All the compounds are coloured, insoluble in benzene, ether and carbon disulphide, but sparingly soluble in ethanol and acetone. The compounds formed with monoamines are, however, sparingly soluble in carbon disulphide. These are fairly stable in dry atmosphere, but when exposed to moist air for a long time they absorb moisture and decompose, compounds formed with diamines being more stable than those with monoamines. The aqueous extract of the compounds responds to the test for chloride, showing thereby that chlorine is in an ionizable state. These compounds are decomposed by acids and alkalis.

When heated alone the compounds decompose before melting, give a sublimate which is soluble in water, acidic and responds to tests for chloride and amine. The compounds with monoamines afford this sublimate at lower temperatures than those with diamines. When heated with soda lime the corresponding amine separates out and condenses in the cooler part of the tube,

TABLE I

A. Compound of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride with primary monoamines

Amines.	Compound formed.	Colour.	%Tungsten.		%Chlorine.		%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Aniline	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{NH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Yellowish green	26.05	25.77	19.24	19.86	7.72	7.85
2. <i>o</i> -Toluidine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Brown	24.12	23.90	18.56	18.42	..	..
3. <i>m</i> -Toluidine	-Do-	Light brown	23.82	23.90	18.23	18.42	..	..
4. <i>p</i> -Toluidine	-Do-	Light brown	23.98	23.90	18.14	18.42	..	..
5. <i>o</i> -Anisidine	$[\text{WO}(\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Chocolate brown	22.30	22.07	16.50	17.00	6.75	6.72
6. <i>m</i> -Anisidine	-Do-	Ash	22.16	22.07	16.94	17.00	..	..
7. <i>p</i> -Anisidine	-Do-	Light violet	22.51	22.07	16.72	17.00	..	..
8. <i>o</i> -Phenetidine	$[\text{WO}(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Ash	21.02	20.67	15.68	15.93	..	..
9. <i>m</i> -Phenetidine	-Do-	Ash	20.43	20.67	15.60	15.93	..	..
10. <i>p</i> -Phenetidine	-Do-	Yellow	20.80	20.67	15.84	15.93	..	..
11. α -Naphthylamine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_7\text{NH}_2)_4]\text{Cl}_4$	Violet	20.18	20.13	15.16	15.62	6.05	6.13
12. β -Naphthylamine	-Do-	Ash	20.34	20.13	15.33	15.52	..	..

TABLE II

B. Compound of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride with primary diamines.

Amines.	Compound formed.	Colour.	%Tungsten.		%Chlorine.		%Nitrogen.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1. Benzidine	$[\text{WO}(\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Ash	26.14	25.92	19.03	19.98	7.85	7.89
2. <i>o</i> -Tolidine	$[\text{WO}(\text{CH}_3\text{NH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH}_2)_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Light brown	23.87	24.02	18.30	18.61	..	..
3. <i>o</i> -Dianisidine	$[\text{WO}(\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{NH}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Chocolate	22.20	23.17	16.94	17.09	..	..
4. <i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	$[\text{WO}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_4(\text{NH}_2)_2)_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Dark brown	33.17	32.98	25.30	25.43	9.89	10.04
5. <i>m</i> -Phenylenediamine	-Do-	Dirty green	33.04	32.98	25.12	25.42	..	..
6. <i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	-Do-	Blue	32.79	32.98	25.36	25.42	..	..
7. <i>m</i> -Tolylenediamine	$[\text{WO}\{\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NH}_2)_2\}_2]\text{Cl}_4$	Blue	31.28	31.41	23.66	24.20	..	..

DISCUSSION

In all the cases studied, four molecules of a monoamine or two molecules of a diamine attach themselves to one molecule of tungsten (VI) oxytetrachloride. The amines appear to attach themselves to the central atom, chelate compounds being formed in the case of diamines which are probably responsible for their greater stability, and may be represented as $[WO(4A)] Cl_4$ (where A=monoamine) and $[WO(2D)] Cl_4$ (where D=diamine). The E. A. N. of tungsten does not assume inert gas configuration and therefore the compounds, though stable in the dry atmosphere at the room temperature, begin to hydrolyse slowly as soon as they come into contact with moist air or when treated with water or dilute alkalies.

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